

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 23 – 31 October 2023

Report published: June 2024

**Elephant encounters:
Studying Asian elephants in the hills of
northern Thailand to increase their
welfare and conservation**

มูลนิธิหัวใจรักช้าง
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary
Love. Care. Rescue.

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**Authors:
Aislinn Butron
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**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

Since 2016 Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) has conducted a semi-wild elephant herd research and conservation project in Northern Thailand (Mae Chaem District). From 2018 onwards Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists and KSES research interns have helped with data collection. This report combines digitally recorded data from both groups from 5 May to 31 October 2023.

The observational study encompasses three distinct datasets on six free-roaming semi-wild Asian elephants (*Elephas maximus*): (1) Activity Budgets with continuous and instantaneous sampling, (2) Foraging Ecology via all-occurrence focal sampling and (3) Social Association via scan sampling.

16,216 continuous Activity Budgets sampling minutes were collected. Analyses of the data showed that elephants spent most of their time foraging (69.1%), followed by exploration (4.2%). 683 behaviour counts of instantaneous Activity Budgets sampling showed that the elephants spent most of their time on dusting (17.9%), exploring (17.4%) and scratching (13.5%). Further analyses showed that there is a statistically significant difference between the aforementioned dusting, exploring and scratching and the 16 other behaviours in both continuous and instantaneous data, such as bathing, aggression, lying down and mating, which were all recorded at below 1%. Overall, the activity budgets of the KSES herd are much closer to those observed in wild, rather than captive elephants.

6,164 minutes of Foraging Ecology data revealed that the elephants consume a diverse diet, comprising 77 plant species from sixteen families. Browse was the most common fodder (61.8%), followed by graze (36.9%). Whilst little is known of the natural foraging ecology of elephants in Thailand, it is clear that the KSES consumes a much more varied diet than captive elephants, for which datasets exist. KSES and Biosphere Expeditions encourage those in the elephant industry to recognise the important link between diet and welfare, and to introduce a more varied and richer diet for elephants.

2,108 counts of Social Associations elucidated complex social interactions within the herd, with females having a larger percentage of interactions, which corroborates other studies. In June 2023 a baby calf was born into the herd, revealing an unexpected shift in social interactions. Other studies have shown that elephant mothers and other female family members have been observed to provide social support to newborns for normal development. Interestingly, in the KSES herd, the parents remain close and somewhat segregated, with the father closely involved in rearing. It will be interesting to observe this more, with the aim of publishing a scientific paper on this in 2025.

Overall, analyses provide clear evidence that KSES elephants are closer to wild, rather than captive elephants in all aspects studied. This shows that KSES's hands-off and semi-wild approach to elephant husbandry results in high animal welfare. To publicise this, KSES aims to publish welfare guidelines in 2026. Since the elephant industry is by and large profit-driven, the welfare guidelines will also describe how easy and cost-effective it is to cultivate accessible plants such as grasses and bamboo for the consumption of elephants in captivity.

บทคัดย่อ

นับตั้งแต่ปี 2016 Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) ได้ดำเนินโครงการวิจัยการเลี้ยงโขลงช้างในสภาพกึ่งป่า และโครงการเพื่อการอนุรักษ์ในเขตภาคเหนือของประเทศไทยภาคเหนือ) อำเภอแม่แจ่ม(ตั้งแต่ปี 2018 เป็นต้นมา นักวิทยาศาสตร์ภาคพลเมืองจาก Biosphere Expeditions และ KSES ผู้ช่วยนักวิจัยได้ร่วมกันรวบรวมข้อมูล รายงานฉบับเป็นการเรียบเรียงข้อมูลจากทั้งสองกลุ่ม ที่ได้รับการบันทึกไว้ในรูปแบบดิจิทัล ระหว่างวันที่ 5 พฤษภาคม ถึง 30 ตุลาคม 2023

การศึกษาใช้วิธีการสังเกตโดยตรง เพื่อรวบรวมชุดข้อมูลสามชุดแยกกัน กับช้างสายพันธุ์เอเชีย (*Elephas maximus*) ที่เลี้ยงแบบปล่อยอิสระในสภาพกึ่งป่าจำนวน 6 ตัว: (1) การเฝ้าติดตามกิจกรรมผ่านการสุ่มตัวอย่างแบบชั่วขณะ)instantaneous sampling((2) การดูพฤติกรรมกรรมการหาอาหารผ่านทุกเหตุการณ์เป็นรายตัว)focal sampling(และ (3) พฤติกรรมการเชื่อมโยงทางสังคมผ่านการสุ่มตัวอย่างแบบกวาด)scan sampling(มีการเฝ้าติดตามศึกษาพฤติกรรมของกลุ่มตัวอย่างรวม 16,216 นาที

จากการวิเคราะห์ข้อมูลพบว่าช้างใช้เวลาส่วนใหญ่ในการเดินหาอาหาร (69.1%) รองลงมาคือการสำรวจพื้นที่ (4.2%) การเฝ้าติดตามกิจกรรมผ่านการสุ่มตัวอย่างแบบชั่วขณะ 683 ครั้ง พบว่าช้างใช้เวลาส่วนใหญ่ไปในการคลุกฝุ่น (17.9%) การสำรวจสิ่งที่อยู่รอบตัว (17.4%) และถูไถตัวกับต้นไม้ (13.5%) การวิเคราะห์เพิ่มเติมยังพบอีกว่า มีความแตกต่างอย่างมีนัยยะสำคัญทางสถิติ ระหว่างการคลุกฝุ่น การสำรวจ และการถูไถดังกล่าว พฤติกรรมอื่นๆ อีก 16 รายการ ทั้งข้อมูลต่อเนื่องและฉับพลัน เช่น การอาบน้ำ การแสดงความก้าวร้าว การนอน และการผสมพันธุ์ ซึ่งทั้งหมดบันทึกไว้ต่ำกว่า 1% โดยรวมแล้ว การสำรวจพฤติกรรมโขลงช้างของ KSES นั้นพบว่ามีใกล้เคียงกับช้างป่าในธรรมชาติ มากกว่าช้างที่ถูกกักขังในที่เลี้ยง

ข้อมูลนิเวศวิทยาการหาอาหารความยาว 6,164 นาที พบว่าช้างมีพฤติกรรมการกินอาหารที่หลากหลาย ประกอบด้วยพืช 77 ชนิดจาก 16 วงศ์ ส่วนใหญ่จะเป็นการเลือกกินพืชพรรณชนิดต่างๆ (61.8%) รองลงมาคือหญ้า (36.9%) ในขณะที่เดียวกัน แม้ว่าเราจะมีความรู้เกี่ยวกับพฤติกรรมการหาอาหารในระบบนิเวศของช้างในประเทศไทย แต่ก็เป็นที่แน่ชัดว่าช้างภายใต้การดูแลของ KSES สามารถเลือกกินอาหารที่หลากหลาย มากกว่าช้างในที่เลี้ยง ซึ่งมีข้อมูลบันทึกไว้อยู่แล้ว KSES และ Biosphere Expeditions ขอเรียกร้องให้ผู้ที่เกี่ยวข้องในอุตสาหกรรมช้าง ได้ตระหนักถึงความเชื่อมโยงที่สำคัญระหว่างอาหารและสวัสดิภาพที่ดีของช้าง

และเปิดโอกาสให้ช้างได้กินอาหารที่หลากหลายและมีคุณค่าทางโภชนาการที่เหมาะสมยิ่งขึ้นสำหรับช้าง พฤติกรรมทางสังคมจำนวน 2,108 ครั้ง ได้ชี้ให้เห็นถึงปฏิสัมพันธ์ทางสังคมที่ซับซ้อนภายในฝูง โดยที่ช้างตัวเมียมีปฏิสัมพันธ์กันในส่วนที่มากกว่า สอดคล้องกับงานวิจัยอื่นๆ ในเดือนมิถุนายน 2023 มีลูกช้างเกิดใหม่ในฝูง และเผยให้เห็นถึงการเปลี่ยนแปลงที่ไม่คาดคิดในพฤติกรรมทางสังคม การศึกษาวิจัยอื่นๆ พบว่า แม่ช้างและช้างตัวเมียอื่นๆ มีพฤติกรรมทางสังคมที่จะสนับสนุนให้ลูกช้างได้เติมโตอย่างเป็นปกติ สิ่งที่น่าสนใจก็คือในโขลงช้างของ KSES พ่อแม่ช้างยังคงอยู่ด้วยกันอย่างใกล้ชิด และคล้ายกับจะแยกตัวออกจากฝูง พ่อช้างมีส่วนร่วมในการเลี้ยงดูอย่างใกล้ชิด พฤติกรรมนี้มีความน่าสนใจและจะได้รับการติดตามอย่างต่อเนื่อง โดยมีเป้าหมายที่จะตีพิมพ์บทความทางวิทยาศาสตร์เกี่ยวกับเรื่องนี้ในปี 2025

โดยรวมแล้ว การวิเคราะห์ได้ชี้ให้เห็นหลักฐานที่ชัดเจนว่าโขลงช้างของ KSES มีความใกล้เคียงกับช้างป่า มากกว่ากว่าช้างในที่เลี้ยงในทุกมิติที่มีการศึกษา และยังสามารถยืนยันได้ว่าแนวทางการดูแลช้างของ KSES แบบปล่อยอิสระ ในสภาพกึ่งป่าส่งผลให้มีสวัสดิภาพสัตว์ในระดับสูง เพื่อเป็นการประชาสัมพันธ์ผลการศึกษานี้ KSES มีเป้าหมายที่จะตีพิมพ์แนวทางปฏิบัติด้านสวัสดิภาพสัตว์ ในปี 2026 เนื่องจากอุตสาหกรรมช้างนั้นมีความจำเป็นต้องขับเคลื่อนด้วยผลกำไร แนวทางปฏิบัติด้านสวัสดิภาพสัตว์จะชี้ให้เห็นถึงความสะดวกง่ายดาย และประหยัดต้นทุน ด้วยการปลูกพืชอาหาร เช่นหญ้าและไม้ไผ่สำหรับช้างในที่เลี้ยง

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1. Expedition Review

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Johncola et al. (2019). This expedition conducted close-encounter studies on a herd of six Asian elephants at Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) in the hills of Northern Thailand. All studies were solely observational with no interaction between the elephants and researchers.

1.2. Dates & team

The expedition ran over an 8-day period from 23 to 31 October 2023. The expedition team was composed of national and international citizen scientists, a professional scientist and an expedition leader. The study period was chosen to coincide with the mildest climate in terms of temperature extremes and high forest food availability for the elephants.

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Aislinn Butron, the expedition leader was Anthony Lyons. The expedition team of citizen scientists was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence): Carlo Casolini Dal Bo (USA), Elena Dormer (Australia), Patricia Ferrara (USA), Neil Goodall (UK), Gary Hogben (UK), Sandra Hogben (UK), Sue Hughes (USA), Phyllis Kristal (USA), Paula Malesa (USA), Susanne Stahl (Germany).

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place and had to be invoked for an arm fracture due to a slip in the shower. The fracture was treated in a local hospital and the casualty was able to continue with the expedition.

1.3. Partners

On this expedition Biosphere Expeditions' main partner was KSES, a fellow nonprofit organisation. Their main objective is to bring elephants back to their natural environment to live in semi-wild conditions and provide an alternative and sustainable livelihood.

1.4. Acknowledgements

The expedition provided labour and funding, and permitted data collection to occur throughout the day, allowing for full data sets on KSES's elephants to be collected. We are grateful to the citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. A big thank you to all the members of the local community, especially those who welcomed expedition participants into their homes with open arms, who guided us through the forest, who helped with transportation and who cooked amazing meals. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank members of the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and donors for their support.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

Project updates, reports and publications:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/thailand-2023/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/thailand>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €2,290 per person per nine-day group towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	22,020
Expenditure	
Staff	4,916
includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	
Research	125
includes equipment and other research expenses	
Transport	452
includes fuel, taxis and other local transport	
Expedition base	2,501
includes board & lodging and base hut upgrade	
Administration	483
includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	
Team recruitment Thailand	7,334
as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	
Income – Expenditure	6,209
Total percentage spent directly on project	72%

2. Activity budgeting, foraging and social behaviour of free-roaming semi-wild Asian elephants

Aislinn Butron
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary

2.1. Introduction

Population dynamics of wild & captive elephants in Thailand

Asian elephants (*Elephas maximus*) are megaherbivores and a keystone species with a wide span of habitat presence, ranging from tropical to sub-tropical regions (Suksavate et al. 2019). The global population is between 40,000-52,000 individuals and the species is categorised as Endangered by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN 2020). In Thailand, the estimated total number of elephants ranges from 6783-7283, with 3783 held in captivity and 3000-3500 in the wild (Thitaram et al. 2015, Asian Elephant Specialist Group 2017). Following global trends, Thailand's elephant population is in decline due to habitat loss, habitat fragmentation and anthropogenic pressure.

History and cultural significance of Asian elephants in Thailand

Elephants have been a fundamental part of Thai culture since the 13th century (Bansiddhi et al. 2020), with animals playing a role in warfare, religion, culture, logging, and now tourism. Industrialisation brought a steep decline in forest cover, resulting in a decline in wild elephant populations. In 1989 the logging industry was banned with 25% of forest cover remaining. Subsequently, the demand for agricultural land, loss of habitat and habitat fragmentation left 70% of working elephants out of a home and out of work. Many elephants together with their caretakers (mahouts) were forced to earn a living in major cities, which created dangerous environments for the public. As a result, the Thai government began to classify elephant populations into wild and captive elephants. Wild populations were under the protection of the Wild Animal Reservation and Protection Act 1992, which prohibits capturing, killing and injuring elephants (Nijman 2014).

Rewilding and wild elephant populations in Thailand

The dramatic decrease in wild elephant populations led to efforts to increase and stabilise their numbers. In 1997 HRH Queen Sirikit of Thailand created the first project to introduce formerly captive elephants to national parks. Since then, 104 elephants have been released (Mithapala 2009, Thitaram et al. 2015, Baker & Winkler 2020). However, there are limitations to rewilding projects due to habitat loss, habitat fragmentation and human-elephant conflict. There is also often increased conflict with humans, for example through crop raiding, where there is reintroduction of captive elephants.

Captive elephant populations in Thailand

Captive elephants are considered livestock in Thailand and are not granted animal welfare protection by the Draught Animal Act of 1939 (Nijman 2014). Traditionally, captive elephants in Thailand were working animals. Today, and for the past five decades, elephants have been working predominantly in tourism (Bansiddhi et al. 2020), which is also an increasingly important factor in Thailand's economy: 21.6% of national gross domestic product according to the Travel & Tourism Council (2020). This growth in tourism in general also results in an increased demand for animal-based tourism, especially elephant tourism. The National Institute of Elephant Research, Health Service, and Department of Livestock Development estimates that there are a minimum of 2700 elephants working in 250 tourist venues throughout Thailand (Bansiddhi et al. 2020). Activities with elephants range from observation, feeding, bathing, walking, riding and elephant shows. However, there are increasing concerns about elephant welfare as well as exploitative and abusive treatment.

Current welfare implications

In Thailand, ethical welfare standards and animal-based tourism do not co-exist naturally (Bansiddhi et al 2018). This, alongside the challenges of too many elephants in too few wild spaces and the difficulties of reintroduction, results in lively and often acrimonious debates about what to do with Thailand's elephants (ASEAN 2015, Schmidt-Burbach 2017, Bansiddhi et al. 2018, Baker & Winkler 2020). For example, Bansiddhi et al. (2018) argue that tourist camps are the only viable solution for providing care for captive elephants, as the demand for elephants in the tourism industry is unlikely to wane in the near future. Baker & Winkler (2020) argue that campaigns to educate tourists might encourage tourist companies to shift activities with elephants to more welfare-oriented hands-off programmes.

Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary project

Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) is an NGO focused on creating an alternative option regarding captive elephant tourism. Its main mission is to bring back elephants to the forest by offering hands-off elephant tourism, which helps provide an income for the elephant mahouts, and the local community, while also allowing the elephants to exhibit natural behaviours. The hands-off tourist programme allows guests to hike to see elephants in their natural habitat. The project also focuses on improving the welfare standards of elephants by conducting research. Currently, KSES's research efforts focus on elephant foraging ecology, behaviour and social association. By collecting, analysing and publishing data in the scientific and industry literature, KSES brings more clarity to a complex situation and develops alternative approaches that are beneficial for elephants and humans. For example, in 2020, KSES published its first research paper (Schwarz et al. 2020) that identified over 160 species of plants consumed by elephants. In 2025, KSES anticipates publishing a second research paper on elephant behaviour, followed by an elephant welfare guide in 2026. Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists and KSES research volunteers are central to that effort.

2.2 Methods

KSES has been gathering data since 2016. The data presented in this annual report encompass digital collections from May to October 2023. During this period, daily trekking expeditions were organised to collect data on six elephants (Table 2.2a) within a 4000-hectare plot of land (Schwarz et al., 2020; Gale & Hammer, 2018). In line with the findings of de Sherbinin et al. (2021) who demonstrated that citizen scientists with adequate training and guidance can add valuable resources and collect reliable data, international citizen scientists actively participated in the collection of various datasets, including foraging ecology, activity budgets, social associations, and biodiversity identification.

Table 2.2a. Elephants in the study herd.

Elephant	Sex	Age (years)
Too Mae	F	60
Mae Doom	F	Approximately 28
Sri Prai	F	Approximately 14
Gen Thong	M	11
Dodo	M	18
Boon Rott	M	18

Training

There were two groups of citizen scientists: Firstly, interns (undergraduate science students) who arrived throughout the study period and who stayed between five to sixty days and were trained individually for three days on arrival. Secondly, Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists (laypeople, by and large without any science training or background) who came in one group of nine days from 23 to 31 October 2023 and were trained en masse during the first two days of their expedition.

Both groups received intensive training, including KSES's aims for the research collected, the three distinct datasets, elephant identification and how to use the KOBO collect app. Additional in-field training was given as needed. Each member collecting data had to undertake a reliability test and had to pass with a minimum grade of 90% before collecting data. The purpose of the reliability test was to ensure that all data collected was consistent, dependable, and comparable to that collected by the scientist and staff members of the project. Data collection was done under the supervision of trained staff members in order to reduce bias and any errors.

For the majority of the year, KSES's data collection involved interns hiking into the forest, covering distances ranging from 5 to 10 km, to locate the elephants. Each dataset was then gathered over a period of 90 minutes. Staff members and interns alike were assigned a specific elephant to monitor and collect activity budgets and foraging ecology. For social associations, the main objective was to document all elephants present within a visible range. Data set collection was predominately conducted in the morning starting at 08:00 and concluding at 12:00, with additional afternoon hikes that took place three times a week for a period of 30 minutes for activity budgets (15:00-16:00).

For Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists, data collection intervals were larger, which allowed for a greater pool of data to be recorded within the nine-day expedition. The observation period began at 08:00 and concluded at 16:00, for one-hour period intervals. All data recorded within the project was purely observational with no interactions between elephants and citizen scientists.

Activity budgets

Since the introduction of digital data collection, activity budgets have been restructured to encompass continuous and instantaneous behaviours. Data are recorded via continuous focal sampling. The observer documents the behaviours displayed by an individual elephant using a behavioural ethogram (Table 2.2b).

Foraging ecology

Data were collected via all occurrence focal sampling, with the observer gathering data on a specific elephant and noting the start and end times of each foraging activity for a specific plant. When an elephant was found consuming a plant species, the observer asked the mahout for the name of the plant species in Karen. The Karen name was later converted to common name and scientific name. GPS coordinates were automatically captured by the KOBO collection app to provide additional information about the plant species.

Social association

Data collection included five-minute scan sampling of all elephants visible within the study range. For each individual elephant a scan of the nearest neighbour, next neighbour and approximate distances were recorded. The distances were categorised as (1) touching, (2) two trunks reach – approximately 3 m, (3) one elephant length apart – approximately 6 m, or (4) over 6 m apart.

Statistical analysis

All data gathered were analysed using Microsoft Excel analysing tools. In the activity budgets dataset, total minutes displaying a specific behaviour were recorded as continuous, whereas all instantaneous behaviours were recorded as counts of activities performed. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed for activity budgets to evaluate any significant differences for both continuous and instantaneous behaviours individually.

For foraging ecology, each species was categorised into specific functional groups such as trees, grasses, shrubs, herbs and bamboo. The functional groups were further classified into browse or graze. Even though bamboo is botanically classified as grass, due to its growth characteristics, bamboo was placed under browse species (following Sukumar 1990, Himmelsbach et al. 2006, Chen et al. 2006, Schwarz et al. 2020). For the purpose of this study, when further diving into functional groups, bamboo was placed into an 'other' category due to the ambiguity in previous papers and the classification of shrub in Joshi (2009). A statistical analysis was performed via a one-way ANOVA to determine whether a significant preference existed between plant type species (climber, trees, shrubs, herbs, grass, bamboo) amongst the elephants. The 'cannot see' and 'undeterminable' dataset were removed from the analysis.

Table 2.2b. Behavioural ethogram used in the field.

Code ID	Behaviour	Description
AT	Agitation	Showing signs of distress due to external factors (motorbike, other animal, loud sounds), that can be exhibited by walking chaotically, raising tail for 5 seconds or more and vocalizing as a form of stress.
AG	Aggression	Threatening behaviour such as standing with ears fanned out or head high, kicking, bumping, or pushing, hitting trunk on the ground or throwing a tantrum.
BA	Bathing	Whole body is immersed in water or having four limbs in water.
DR	Drinking	Using trunk to take water and placing in mouth.
DU	Dusting	Collection of soil with trunk, and throwing it over body.
EX	Exploring	Exploring the environment such as raising trunk to smell, using trunk on the ground to explore the substrate or other objects. As well as stopping previous behaviour, and moving ears straight up, to listen to their surroundings. Does not include foraging behaviour.
FG	Foraging	Placing food in mouth, exploring environment to find new food. Walking towards food.
EI	Elephant interaction	Interacting with other individuals with touch of any body part (Not part of courtship behaviour).
LD	Lying down	Lying down on the ground laterally.
MI	Mahout interaction	Interaction with mahout, solicited or spontaneous.
MA	Mating	Courting or being courted or mounting another elephant or being mounted by another elephant of either sex
MB	Mud bathing	Rolling in mud or using trunk to spray mud on body.
NV	Not visible	Behaviour cannot be recorded, elephant out of view, or cannot distinguish behaviour.
SC	Scratching	Scratching or rubbing any body part with another part of the body, or with an inanimate object
SV	Social vocalising	Communication such as rumbling, trumpeting, squeaking, or roaring.
ST	Stereotyping	Standing still while moving forward or backwards. Bobbing head while standing still. Moving one leg in a forwards and backwards motion.
TU	Tool use	Scratching with stick, fly swatting with branch, throwing branch over body.
WA	Walking	Movement of all four legs in a forward or backward motion. Does not include walking towards food.
OT	Other	Any other behaviour, specify in description box

2.3. Results

Activity Budgets

Each elephant was observed to be exhibiting continuous behaviours, for an average of 2,702 minutes, resulting in a collective total of 16,215 minutes of recorded activities for all elephants. For 1,449 (8.9%) minutes, the elephants were out of the study range ('not visible'). Out of the 19 behaviours listed on the ethogram (Table 2.2b), the elephants exhibited 18 behaviours (Table 2.3a). Mating was the only behaviour not observed. The activities aggression, agitation, bathing, dusting, lying down, mahout interaction, scratching, social vocalisation, stereotyping, tool use and other were recorded at less than 1% (Table 2.3a). There was a statistically significant difference in continuous behaviours observed for the six individual elephants ($F=141.6$, $p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.3a. Percentage of total minutes of continuous behaviours.

Code ID	Behaviour	Percentage of total minutes of continuous behaviours
FG	Foraging	69.5%
NV	Not visible	9.0%
EX	Exploring	4.8%
WA	Walking	3.7%
EI	Elephant interaction	3.1%
MB	Mud bathing	2.1%
DR	Drinking	1.9%
DU	Dusting	1.0%
MI	Mahout interaction	1.0%
SC	Scratching	1.0%
OT	Other	0.9%
TU	Tool use	0.8%
ST	Stereotyping	0.4%
BA	Bathing	0.3%
SV	Social vocalising	0.3%
AT	Agitation	0.1%
LD	Lying down	0.1%
AG	Aggression	<0.01%
MA	Mating	0%

An average of 113 instantaneous activities were observed for each elephant for a grand total of 683 counts. For four counts (0.6%) the elephants were out of sight and recorded as 'not visible'. Out of 19 behaviours within the ethogram (Table 2.2b), 17 behaviours were recorded (Table 2.3b). Dusting was the most prominent instantaneous activity (17.9%), followed by elephant interaction (17.4%). There was a statistically significant difference in instantaneous behaviours recorded for the six individual elephants ($F=2.47$, $p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.3b. Percentage of total count of instantaneous behaviours.

Code ID	Behaviour	Percentage of total minutes of instantaneous behav.
DU	Dusting	17.9%
EI	Elephant interaction	17.4%
SC	Scratching	13.5%
EX	Exploring	10.0%
FG	Foraging	8.8%
WA	Walking	7.8%
SV	Social vocalising	7.6%
MI	Mahout interaction	7.3%
TU	Tool use	3.7%
ST	Stereotyping	1.8%
AT	Agitation	1.5%
DR	Drinking	1.2%
NV	Not visible	0.6%
AG	Aggression	0.6%
MB	Mud bathing	0.3%
BA	Bathing	0.2%
MA	Mating	0.2%

When comparing continuous and instantaneous behaviours, foraging was mainly observed in a continuous dataset at 31.5% and elephant interaction at 10.6% as opposed to instantaneous at 8.8% and 17.4%, respectively (Figure 2.3a). However, scratching was observed as instantaneous at a percentage of 13.5% and continuous at 6.2%. Dusting was also noted at a higher percentage as instantaneous behaviour at 17.9% versus 6.1% for continuous behaviours. The remaining behaviours such as aggression, bathing and mating were observed at less than 1%. Some behaviours were observed at higher percentages in the instantaneous dataset, such as social vocalisation 7.6%, stereotyping 1.8%, mahout interaction 7.3% than their counterpart in the continuous dataset. Other behaviours were examined to be of a higher percentage in the continuous dataset such as drinking 2.5%, exploration 11.9%, mud bathing 2.2% and not visible at 5.8%.

A comparison between morning and afternoon observational times was conducted to determine frequency of activities in relation to the time of day (Figure 2.3b). More variance of instantaneous behaviours as opposed to continuous behaviours was observed in the morning dataset (Figure 2.3c).

Figure 2.3a Percentage count comparison between continuous and instantaneous behaviours.

Figure 2.3b. Percentage count comparisons of instantaneous behaviours during morning and afternoon data collection periods.

Figure 2.3c. Percentage count comparison of continuous behaviours during morning and afternoon data collection periods.

Social association

The six elephants displayed varied social preferences. The male bulls within the herd were seen to have fewer interactions than the females in both 'nearest neighbour' (Figure 2.3d) and 'next nearest neighbour' (Figure 2.3e) datasets.

256 data points were collected on Mae Doom. She had the most 'nearest neighbour' social interactions at 27.2% of interactions. Mae Doom's social preference for 'nearest neighbour' was at a distance of six metres or more, at 13.5%. She was found to be touching another elephant at 2.4%, two trunk's reach at 9.1% and less than six metres at 2.3%. Her highest social preference amongst the herd was found to be with Gen Thong, with 8.2% of interactions and Too Meh at 7.5%, with most interactions recorded at over 6 metres. However, Sri Prai was at a closer proximity (touching and two trunk's reach) at 5.1%. Lastly, Mae Doom had the least 'nearest neighbour' interactions with Boon Rott at 4.1% and Dodo at 1.7%. For 'next nearest neighbour', 216 data points were collected at a rate of 25.7% of interactions. Mae Doom was found to have the highest percentage of interactions with Too Meh at 12.7%, with the majority of interactions taking place at a distance of six metres or more. Amongst the remaining elephants, she had interactions with Gen Thong (6.2%), Boon Rott (3.4%), Sri Prai (1.8%) and Dodo (1.5%). There was a significant difference between the type of interactions.

214 data points were collected on Too Meh, the matriarch of the herd. She had the third most 'nearest neighbour' social interactions at 15.2% of interactions. Too Meh's social preference 'nearest neighbour' was at a distance of six metres or more at 9.2%. She was found to be touching at 1.5%, two trunk's reach at 2.9% and less than 6 metres at 1.55%. Her social preference amongst the herd was found to be Boon Rott with an interaction of 5.87%, then Mae Doom at 4.24% and Gen Thong at 3.18% with most interactions at varying distances. However, Mae Doom was found to be at a closer proximity (touching and two trunk's reach) at 1.7%. Lastly, Too Meh had the least 'nearest neighbour' interactions with Sri Prai at 1.1% and Dodo at 0.7%. For 'next nearest neighbour', 244 data points collected at a rate of 21.2% of interactions. Too Meh was found to have the highest percentage of interactions with Gen Thong at 7.8% and Mae Doom at 7.4%, with the majority of interactions taking place at a distance of six metres or more. The remaining elephants she had interactions with were Sri Prai at 3.5%, Boon Rott at 2.4%, and Dodo at 0.1%. There was a significant difference between the type of interactions.

228 data points were collected on Sri Prai, the youngest female of the herd, not related to any other elephants. She had the second most 'nearest neighbour' social interactions at 21.7% of interactions. Sri Prai's social preference 'nearest neighbour' was at a distance of six metres or more at 8.3% and two trunk's reach at 8.2%. She was found to be touching at 3.8% and less than six metres at 1.3%. Her social preference amongst the herd was Dodo with an interaction of 10.6%, with interactions at varying distances. However, Sri Prai was found to be at a closer proximity to Mae Doom (touching and two trunk's reach) at 5.1%. Lastly, she had the least 'nearest neighbour' interactions with Too Meh at 2.2%, Gen Thong at 2.3% and Boon Rott at 0.3%. For 'next nearest neighbour', 91 data points were collected at a rate of 12.0% of interactions. She was found to have the highest percentage of interactions with Too Meh at 4.1%, however the majority of interactions took place at a distance of six metres or more. The remaining elephants she had interactions were Mae Doom (3.0%), Gen Thong (2.8%), Dodo (1.6%) and Boon Rott (0.6%) at varying distances.

For the youngest male in the study, Gen Thong, 197 data points were collected. He had 'nearest neighbour' social interactions at 14.9% of interactions. Gen Thong's social preference 'nearest neighbour' was at a distance of six metres or more at 8.3%, followed by two trunk's reach at 4.2%. He was found to be touching at 1.0%, and less than six metres at 1.4%. His social preference amongst the herd was Mae Doom, with an interaction of 7.1%, with his preference of interaction to be two trunk's reach at 2.7% and 6 metres or more at 3.7%. His second most preferred interaction was with Boon Rott at 3.4%, with most interactions being six or more metres apart at 2.4%. He had fewer interactions with Too Meh at 2.9%, followed by Sri Prai at 1.1% and lastly Dodo at 0.2%. All of these interactions were at varied distances. For 'next nearest neighbour', 206 data points were collected at a rate of 20.2% of interactions. He was found to have the highest percentage of interactions with Too Meh (8.6%) and Mae Doom (5.3%), however the majority of interactions varied between two trunk's reach, 6 metres or less and more than 6 metres. The remaining elephants he had interactions with were with Boon Rott (2.7%), Sri Prai (1.8%), and Dodo (1.7%). All interactions excluded touching.

168 data points were collected on Boon Rott, a male elephant that is unrelated to the rest of the herd. He had 'nearest neighbour' social interactions at 8.6% of interactions. Boon Rott's social preference 'nearest neighbour' was at a distance at six metres or more at 5.5%, followed by two trunk's reach (2.0%). He was found to be touching at 0.3%, and less than six metres at 0.7%. His social preference amongst the herd was Too Meh with an interaction of 3.9% followed by Gen Thong (2.3%) and Mae Doom (2.2%), with his preference of interaction varying between the distances. He had lowest interactions at a preference of two trunk's reach with Sri Prai (0.1%), followed by Dodo (0.1%). 80 data points were collected at a rate of 16.1% for 'next nearest neighbour' interactions. He was found to have the highest percentage of interactions with Mae Doom at 7.2% and Gen Thong at 5.2%. However, the majority of interactions varied between two trunk's reach, six metres or less and more than six metres. The remaining elephants, he had interactions with were with Too Meh (2.0%), Sri Prai (1.6%), and Dodo (0.1%). All interactions excluded touching.

164 data points were collected on Dodo, a male elephant that is part of the three generations of the herd. He had the least interactions amongst all the elephants, with 'nearest neighbour' social interactions at 12.5%. Dodo's social preference 'nearest neighbour' was at a distance of six metres or more at 5.7%, followed by two trunk's reach (4.2%). He was found to be touching at 1.6%, and less than six metres at 0.9%. His social preference amongst the herd was Sri Prai, with an interaction of 10.5%, with his preference of interaction varying between the distances. He had significantly lower interactions with the rest of the herd, with Mae Doom at 1.0%, followed by Too Meh at 0.9% and lastly Gen Thong at 0.01%. The interactions with Mae Doom and with Too Meh varied between the distances. However, the only distance recorded with the youngest male Gen Thong was touching. He had no interactions with Boon Rott, the oldest male bull. 44 'next nearest neighbour' data points were collected at a rate of 4.8% of interactions. He was found to have the highest percentage of interactions with Mae Doom at 1.7%, followed by Sri Prai at 1.6% and Gen Thong at 1.3%. However, the interactions excluded touching. His lowest percentage of interaction was with Too Meh at 0.2%, with the interactions observed only at a distance of six metres or more. No interactions were observed between Dodo and Boon Rott for the dataset of 'next nearest neighbour'.

Figure 2.3d. Nearest neighbour associations.

Figure 2.3e. Next nearest neighbour associations.

Foraging

A total of 6,242 minutes of foraging data were collected, with 77 different species of plants consumed, 47 of which were identified to the genus, 16 to family level and 14 to local names.

The plants consumed and identified come from 31 different families: Fabaceae (ten species), Poaceae (10), Anacardiaceae (4), Dipterocarpaceae (3), Moraceae (3), Rubiaceae (3) and Fagaceae (3). Two species were found for Burseraceae, Tiliaceae, Zingiberaceae and Phyllanthaceae. One species each was found in the following families: Primulaceae, Dioscoreaceae, Araliaceae, Arecaceae, Solanaceae, Vitaceae, Malvaceae, Menispermaceae, Celastraceae, Apocynaceae, Costaceae, Asteraceae, Commelinaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Lamiaceae, Musaceae, Clusiaceae, Myrsinaceae, Sapindaceae, and Annonaceae (Table 2.3c).

The six elephants consumed 61.8% browse species (bamboo, climbers, trees, shrubs, and herbs) and 36.9% grasses. (Bamboo was classified as ‘other’ within the five functional groups (climber, grasses, shrubs, trees, herbs) due to the ambiguity in previous papers and the classification of shrub in Joshi (2009). Two types of bamboo were consumed at 19.5%, followed by herbs at 15.5%) (Table 2.3c). Seventeen new species (1.3%) were collected and are currently awaiting submission for review by a botanist (Table 2.3c). Moreover, an additional 13 species are currently under review by a botanist and remain unidentified, but comprise six trees, two climbers, two shrubs, two grasses and one herb. There was a statistically significant difference between the means of the five functional groups ($F=4.089$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 2.3c Plant species and parts consumed in percentages, classified under Karen (in parentheses) and Botanical name in 2023

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
(Vami) Poaceae	Other	Leaves, roots, shoot, stem, whole plant	17.53%
(Vasu) Poaceae	Other	Leaves, stem	2.00%
<i>Pachyrhizus sp.</i> (Bloor moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem	0.32%
<i>Pueraria sp.</i> (Gopomu) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem, twig, roots, whole plant	0.38%
<i>Tinospora sp.</i> (Duh suh key) Menispermaceae	Climber	Leaves, twig	0.08%
(Dah ugh juh moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem	0.10%
<i>Ficus religiosa L.</i> (Cley) Moraceae	Climber	Whole plant	0.02%
<i>Paederia foetida</i> (Chewie et non a moo) Rubiaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem, twig, whole plant	1.38%
<i>Celastrus paniculatus Willd.</i> (Duh si blu) Celastraceae	Climber	Leaves, stem, whole plant	0.13%
<i>Dioscorea sp.</i> (New-ay me amoo) Dioscoreaceae	Climber	Leaves	0.34%
Unidentified (Guhsee padoh)	Climber	Leaves, stem, twig	0.35%

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
Unidentified (Hoh)	Climber	Leaves, bark	0.14%
(See lee dee a moo) Apocynaceae	Climber	Stem, whole plant	0.08%
<i>Spatholobus sp.</i> (Qui bah moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, bark, roots, stem, twig, whole plant	2.80%
<i>Zea mays</i> (Bukessa) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	2.60%
(Non check ko) Poaceae	Grass	Whole plant	1.38%
<i>Pennisetum polystachyon (L.) Schult.</i> (Noh gwah) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, twig, whole plant	22.11%
(Noh rey) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	1.70%
(Geh meh or Gammay) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, whole plant	0.77%
(Neh pee-ah) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	4.04%
Unidentified (Guh hee) <i>Cyrtococcum accrescens (Trin.) Stapf</i> (Noh vah deh) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, whole plant	0.88%
(Chew meh bwee) (Po pah du) Zingiberaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	0.62%
(Noh or Door moo) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves	0.03%
Unidentified (Hoh duh doh)	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	2.39%
(Puh) Zingiberaceae	Herb	Leaves, stem, shoot, whole plant	15.54%
<i>Cheilocostus speciosus</i> (Le bow) Costaceae	Herb	Whole plant	0.08%
<i>Crassocephalum crepidioides (Benth.) S. Moore</i> (Duh boo dah) Asteraceae	Herb	Leaves, stem	0.03%
<i>Commelina paludosa Blume</i> (Goh poh doh) Commelinaceae	Herb	Whole plant	0.11%
<i>Solanum torvum Sw.</i> (Suh go caw) Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves, whole plant	0.24%
(Lah nee) Vitaceae	Shrub	Leaves, stem, bark	0.14%
<i>Manihot esculenta Crantz</i> (Nuway say) Euphorbiaceae	Shrub	Leaves, stem, bark	0.18%
Unidentified (Say gloh boh)	Shrub	Leaves	0.02%
Unidentified (Grey tee) <i>Broussonetia papyrifera (L.) L'Hér. Ex Vent.</i> (Sah lay dah) Moraceae	Shrub	Bark	0.11%
Unidentified (Say cheh roh)	Shrub	Leaves	0.05%
Unidentified (Buh doh meh)	Tree	Bark	0.03%
	Tree	Leaves	0.08%
	Tree	Bark	0.26%

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
<i>Dalbergia sp.</i> (Ta claw) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.06%
Unidentified (Qwah)	Tree	Leaves	0.14%
<i>Ficus subpisocarpa</i> Gagnep. (Kluh lah) Moraceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig	0.34%
Unidentified (Say beh me)	Tree	Bark	0.45%
Unidentified (Hoh boh)	Tree	Bark	0.19%
<i>Archidendron sp.</i> (Poat du sue or Say duh) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.06%
<i>Quercus sp.</i> (Say qui bwah) Fagaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, twig	0.22%
(Say toe qui) Rubiaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, bark	1.55%
(Poca) Rubiaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark	0.32%
<i>Albizia sp.</i> (Buchee) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, twig, bark	0.58%
(Dah sway) Tiliaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.10%
<i>Tectona grandis</i> (Buh he) Lamiaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.02%
<i>Musa spp.</i> (Suh qwee) Musaceae	Tree	Bark	0.13%
<i>Cratoxylum formosum</i> (C'est qweh cho) Clusiaceae	Tree	Leaves, twig, bark	0.75%
<i>Radermachera</i> (La bodeh) Araliaceae/Bignoniaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.05%
<i>Aporosa villosa</i> (Wall. ex Lindl.) Baill. (Buh krew) Phyllanthaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem	0.05%
<i>Dalbergia sp.</i> (Sahree) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark	0.19%
<i>Ardisia sp.</i> (Cho me gee do daw) Myrsinaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.14%
<i>Solanum erianthum</i> D. Don (Sah koh blee)	Tree	Fruit, roots, stem, bark, twig	1.71%
<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> Spreng. (Sah coo rae) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves, twig	0.02%
<i>Gluta usitata</i> (Wall.) Ding Hou (Su) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, twig, bark	0.11%
<i>Mangifera sp.</i> (Sokosa) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.08%
<i>Shorea obtuse</i> (Lah boh) Dipterocarpaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, roots	1.39%
<i>Dimocarpus longan</i> (Guh geh luh) Sapindaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.03%
<i>Quercus kerrii</i> Craib (Sah gay prah) Fagaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.08%
<i>Aporosa villosa</i> (Wall. ex Lindl.) Baill. (Buh kah bey) Phyllanthaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.08%
<i>Dipterocarpus tuberculatus</i> Roxb. (La tuh) Dipterocarpaceae	Tree	Leaves, twig, bark, stem	0.10%

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
(Nah toh joh) Annonaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.06%
<i>Embelia sp.</i> (Ta bla chee) Primulaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, bark	0.11%
<i>Spondias pinnata</i> (L.f.) Kurz (Makoo) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves, roots, bark	1.11%
<i>Bauhinia sp.</i> (Guh huh) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.10%
<i>Grewia eriocarpa</i> Juss. (Sah bloh bley) Tiliaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig	0.29%
<i>Sterculia foetida</i> L. (Koh) Malvaceae	Tree	Bark, twig	1.68%
(Suh duh) Burseraceae	Tree	Bark	0.61%
<i>Pentacme siamensis</i> (Hcho) Dipterocarpaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig	3.86%
<i>Protium serratum</i> Engl. (Suh pee) Burseraceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig, stem	2.18%
<i>Tamarindus indica</i> (Samoclay) Fabaceae	Tree	Fruit	0.10%
<i>Castanopsis sp.</i> (S-eh) Fagaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.19%
<i>Phoenix loureiroi</i> Kunth (Lee kaw doo) Arecaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.06%

2.4. Discussion and conclusions

Activity budgets

The elephants of KSES were observed to be prominently foraging (69.5%), which is comparable to wild populations that spend 60-80% of their waking time actively foraging (Baskaran et al. 2010). In wild population studies, elephants are observed to eat for 16 hours a day, primarily due to the low-quality vegetation that allows for only 35-46% of food to be digested (McKay 1973; Stoinski et al. 2000; Roehrs et al. 1989; Shoshani & Eisenberg 1982; Lukacs et al. 2016). As a result, wild elephants need to devote a substantial amount of time consuming an abundance of food to meet their nutritional needs. In contrast it is reasonable to assume that captive elephants spend a shorter amount of time foraging due to the accessibility of prepared foods. For KSES, within morning and afternoon datasets, the elephants spent the majority of their time foraging at a higher percentage in comparison to other behaviours, a similar pattern was also observed by Dublin Zoo (Brady et al. 2021). Additionally, based on previous studies, the shift from 'mahout owners' (individuals who both own and work directly with their elephants) to 'remote owners' (individuals who possess ownership, but do not engage directly in the care of their elephants) has resulted in a decrease in the overall foraging time for captive elephants (Lair 1997; Baker & Winkler 2020). KSES works by collaborating with both the 'remote owner,' as well as 'mahout owners'. Although KSES is involved with both types of owners, foraging behaviours have not decreased, but rather remained comparable to wild elephants, which provides strong evidence that our combined management strategy is advantageous to the welfare of elephants.

Walking was recorded as the third most prominent behaviour. Wild Asian elephants are expected to travel distances of 5-10 km per day, with variable amounts on a daily basis depending on availability of foraging resources (Brady et al. 2021). It is feasible that walking within this study occurred at a higher frequency than what was observed since walking was also a result of exploring the environment or foraging, which were recorded separately. Additionally, the walking behaviour is comparable to elephants studied within the Dublin Zoo by Brady et al. (2021) who were observed to have similar locomotion patterns in comparison to the wild population within our study. The Dublin Zoo study concluded that a reduction in locomotion is known to cause health issues such as obesity, arthritis, and foot issues. This suggests the need to provide adequate habitats that meet their locomotory and foraging needs, especially for elephants in captivity where resources tend to be in fixed locations (Brady et al. 2021, Glaeser et al. 2021).

Stereotypic behaviour at KSES was noted at a comparatively low percentage, differing from other studies. However, unlike at KSES, these studies also included nocturnal observations and reported a heightened frequency of stereotypic behaviour during nocturnal hours. For example, Rees (2008), in a study at Chester Zoo (UK), identified a higher percentage of stereotypic behaviour later on in the day as well as higher percentages when food availability was scarce. The elephants at KSES exhibit low percentages of stereotypic behaviour throughout the day, because they can roam freely and are able to socialise and forage. It is important to note, however, that the KSES herd was not observed during nocturnal hours. Vanitha et al. (2015) and Webber et al. (2017) found that stereotypic behaviour was more prevalent in younger bulls if they were unable to develop strong social bonds. The three males in our study were previously kept in confinement in tourist camps, where they were unable to socialise properly, making them more likely to exhibit stereotypic behaviour. More data are needed to determine this pattern. Additionally, with the introduction of a calf at KSES, a further study is under development to determine the semi-wild calf's behaviour, and early stages of calf development including the effect that normal foraging and socialising has on the frequency stereotypic behaviour.

Elephants within the KSES study are not required to work (logging or as a close interaction tourist attraction). In line with KSES's observation only policy, elephants are free to display natural behaviours. According to a study conducted in the timber industry in Myanmar on semi-captive elephants, aggression was observed at a high frequency. The elephants in that study worked in the logging industry during the day, but were allowed to forage, mate and socialise at night with other captive and wild elephants (Seltmann et al 2018). The elephants at KSES exhibited agitation, aggression and stereotypic patterns below 2% in both continuous and instantaneous datasets, providing more strong evidence that hands-off semi-wild conditions are conducive to high animal welfare.

Dusting behaviour was the most prominent instantaneous behaviour exhibited by the KSES herd, most likely to regulate body temperature and protect skin from radiation and insect bites (Rees 2002). Since 2023 brought record-breaking temperatures in Asia, it is not surprising that this behaviour was observed at higher rates.

Social association

In a study conducted on sociable personalities displayed in semi-captive Asian elephants, aggressiveness was observed to be higher in male bulls, while females tended to score higher in sociability (Seltmann et al. 2019). Female Asian elephants tend to live in small close-bonded units, which may indicate a preference for maintaining close proximity (Seltmann et al. 2019). Within KSES, the three females had higher rates of nearest neighbour interactions. Two members of the herd are mother and daughter (Too Meh and Mae Doom) and they tended to be in close proximity to each other. The third female (Sri Prai) recently became a mother, therefore highlighting the essential need for a cohesive herd as elephants live in family-oriented multi-hierarchy societies and can experience complex social interactions throughout their lifetime (Seltmann et al 2018; Sukumar 2003, Moss et al. 2011). The three KSES females showed a preference for higher sociability than the males, corroborating Seltmann et al. (2019) who describe a more affectionate demeanour and eagerness to seek out others for company in females.

While the male bulls within the KSES study were less sociable in comparison to the females, the males were within the 'nearest neighbour' dataset, at distances greater than six metres. Although little is known about the social structure of males, males have been observed to live in solitary or within bachelor herds, only to associate with females during musth (Seltmann et al. 2018, Sukumar 2003). The male KSES bulls do not reflect the findings of previous studies and may exhibit greater sociability, possibly due to their introduction as young bulls and the relatively small size of our herd (Seltmann et al. 2018, Sukumar 2003).

In June of 2023 a baby calf was born to Dodo (father) and Sri Prai (mother), thus altering the social dynamic of the KSES herd. Before giving birth, Sri Prai had various social interactions with the rest of herd. After giving birth, the mother and father started displaying social preference for each other, as well segregating themselves from the herd at various times. Elephant mothers and other female family members have been observed to provide social support to newborns for normal development (Webber et al. 2017, Lee 1987, Lee & Moss 1999 & 2011). This differs from our results, as Dodo remains a prevalent figure in the calf's life whilst also creating a family unit with the mother. It is recommended to observe and analyse the social interactions between Sri Prai, Dodo and their offspring to investigate social development further.

Foraging

When comparing our results from the past six months to that of Schwarz et al. (2020), KSES elephants exhibit a similar preference for browse over graze. This is further corroborated by a study in China (Chen et al. 2006). According to Kane (2005), browse species are essential in the diet of elephants, as well as fulfilling all the dietary needs of captive elephants. Schwarz et al. (2020) and Himmelsbach et al. (2006), like this study, also observed a preference for bamboo (this study at 17.8%). We believe that elephants may exhibit a preference for easier foliage such as bamboo, due to its abundance in the forest during the wet season, as well as fulfilling the dietary requirements of fresh biomass for 10% of their body weight (Sukumar 1989, Karunaratne & Ranawana 1999, Schwarz et al. 2020). However, in contrast to Schwarz et al. (2020), grasses in this study accounted for 36.9%. This is due to the addition of a new plant species with the Karen name of Hoh duh doh (15.5%) that is under review for scientific identification by a botanist.

Hoh duh doh was preferred especially at the beginning of the year, when the elephants had the opportunity to forage in a field that had been previously used for cultivation.

Little is known of the natural foraging ecology of elephants in Thailand, in part due to the lack of studies conducted on wild populations. Through the ongoing collection of foraging ecology data, we can expand our plant database, ensuring it remains up-to-date and provides a useful guideline for feeding captive elephants in Thailand.

Implications for captive elephants and the contribution of this study to elephant welfare and conservation

The collaboration of KSES team (staff and interns) with citizen scientists from Biosphere Expeditions has made data collection on natural behaviours, foraging patterns and elephant social structure possible.

Our analyses provide clear evidence that KSES elephants are closer to wild rather than captive elephants in all aspects studied. This shows that KSES's hands-off and semi-wild approach to elephant husbandry results in high animal welfare. Through these annual reports, publications in the scientific literature and the elephant welfare guidelines to be published in 2026, we hope that this will make others adopt this model and as such increase elephant welfare in Thailand and beyond.

A varied diet is rare in captive elephants (Vanitha, et al 2008) resulting in low animal welfare. We hope that our continuing foraging ecology study will be utilised by those in the elephant industry to recognise the important link between diet and welfare, and to introduce a more varied and richer diet for elephants. Since the elephant industry is by and large profit-driven, the welfare guidelines will describe how easy and cost-effective it is to cultivate easily accessible plants such as grasses and bamboo for the consumption by elephants in captivity.

Showcasing our alternative form of ethical elephant tourism may also provide an impetus for the tourism industry in Thailand to shift in this direction.

Recommendations for the 2024 expedition

- The shift to digital data collection was successful. The project should acquire five more Android research phones, for easier data collection and management.
- The project should acquire six camera traps and/or CCTV cameras for the activity budgets study. With this, an additional study comparing diurnal and nocturnal activities could be conducted for a better understanding of elephant behaviour patterns.
- A publication on activity budgets and social association should be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal by 2025.
- Following the publication of all datasets, an elephant management guide will be created to distribute to other elephant venues in Thailand and around the world by 2026.
- An additional research study of calf development should be conducted on the newest addition to the herd.

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